

The Influence of Work and Communication Facilities on Employee Performance at The Education Department of Labuhan Batu with Motivation as an Intervening Variable

Mursal Rambe¹, Cut Fitri Rostina², Sofiyan³, Robert Tua Siregar⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Universitas Prima Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Employee performance is an indicator of the successful operation of government institutions in achieving their goals. The emergence of achievement is influenced by several driving factors, both from outside the individual and from within the individual. Employee performance greatly determines the progress of a government agency. The performance of each employee can be measured by looking at the quantity and quality of work that has been done. Performance is a very important thing in an organization's efforts to achieve goals. This study aims to determine whether work and communication facilities affect employee performance through motivation as an intervening variable at the Labuhanbatu District Education Office. The study was conducted on 61 employees using a saturated sampling technique. The data collection technique used was primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique used quantitative data which was processed using the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t test, Sobel test and path analysis. The results obtained in this study show 1) there is a significant effect between work facilities on motivation, 2) there is a significant effect between communication variables on motivation, 3) there is a significant effect between work facilities variables on performance, 4) there is a significant effect between communication variables on performance, 5) there is a significant influence between motivational variables on performance, 6) motivational variables can affect work facilities variables on performance, 7) motivational variables can affect communication variables on performance.

KEYWORDS: Communication, Motivation, Performance, Work Facilities.

INTRODUCTION

In an agency, the performance of an employee is an important asset that is needed in supporting and helping to achieve the goals desired by an agency. Therefore, each agency always monitors the performance of its employees in order to continue to improve their performance better. Effective and efficient employee performance is needed by an agency so that it will advance the organization. Employee performance is one of the indicators of the success of the government's glue operation in achieving its goals. The onset of achievement is influenced by several driving factors, both from outside the individual and from within the individual. Employee performance largely determines the progress of a government agency. The performance of the employee's iap set can be measured by looking at the quantity and quality of work he has done. Performance is very important in the organization's efforts to achieve goals. According to Mangkunegara (2014:67), "performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to him". The issue of employee performance is an issue that needs to be considered by the organization, because employee performance will affect the quality of the company in facing competition along with the development of era. An organization in the world of work, both government companies and private companies in carrying out their performance, relies heavily on work facilities or equipment to complete a work efficiently and optimal work results. This statement is supported by previous research conducted by (Anasari & Suryani, 2015) concluded that "There is a significant influence between office facilities and performance employees". This proves that the better the office facilities, the better the employee performance will be.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance is a real behavior that everyone displays as work achievements produced by employees according to their role in the agency. Performance is very important in the agency's efforts to achieve its goals. According to Priansa (2018:269) Performance is the success rate of employees in completing their work. Meanwhile, according to Robbin in Cashmere (2018: 183) Performance is a function of ability, motivation, and opportunity. According to Irianto in Sutrisno (2011:171) Performance is a feat that a person acquires in performing a task. And the success of the organization depends on the performance of the actors of the organization concerned. Meanwhile, according to Mangkunegara (2017: 67) Performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties according to the responsibilities given to him.

Based on the definition above, it can be concluded that performance is a process in carrying out an activity given to employees in accordance with their work and ability to achieve work results and the achievements he has achieved to the maximum in the organization.

Work facilities cannot be ignored in carrying out work operations. Work facilities play a very important role so that organizational operations can be done better, more precisely, and faster. Moenir (2010:197) states, "Facilities as everything that is used, used, forged, by employees both in direct relation to work and for the smooth running of work". Meanwhile, according to Husnan (2002: 187), "Work facilities are facilities and infrastructure needed to help employees to more easily complete work so as to improve their performance". According to Ismaniar (2012:153), "Work facilities are the means provided by companies for the smooth running of activities, with various forms". For example, workplace conditions, such as: lamps or lighting, *air conditioner*; the area of the room, the technology used, such as computers, copiers, facsimiles and so on; as well as other supporting facilities such as prayer rooms, lockers, toilets and so on. Based on this understanding, it can be concluded that work facilities are everything that is used in the form of equipment or tools to facilitate office activities / work so that the purpose of which desirable achieved.

Work facilities are tools used by karywan to make it easier to complete their work. Work facilities at each company will differ in form and type, depending on the type of business and the size of the company.

According to Hamali (2016: 224) Communication is a process of conveying ideas and information in the form of orders and work instructions from a leader to employees or subordinates to carry out tasks work to the best of my ability.

According to Handoko (2012: 272) communication is the process of transferring understanding in the form of ideas or information from a person to another person. The purpose of the communication process is the achievement of *mutual understanding* between the two parties. Before the messages are sent to the communicant, the communicator gives the meanings in the message (*decode*) which are then captured by the communicant and given meaning according to the concept it has (*encode*).

Meanwhile, according to Mangkunegara (2017: 145) Communication can be interpreted as the process of transferring information, ideas, understanding from seseorang to others in the hope that the other person can interpret in accordance with the intended purpose.

Based on some of the understandings above, it can be concluded that communication in organizational life, the achievement of goals with all their homework requires communication. Through communication, it can provide information about work that makes employees act with a sense of responsibility to themselves which at the same time can develop morale of the employees.

Motivasi is an activity that results in a person completing his work with enthusiasm, willingness and full of responsibility. Motivation serves as a driver or encouragement to employees to be willing to work hard for the achievement of their instant goals well, for more details below Understanding motivation according to experts. According to Hasibuan (2009:95) motivation is the provision of driving force that creates the excitement of a person's work, so that they are willing to work together, work effectively, and integrate with all the power of his efforts to achieve satisfaction. Based on the definition that has been put forward from experts, it can be concluded that in providing motivation, it is not separated from the ability of a leader to be able to influence, motivate, directing and communicating with employees. This is related to how leaders can motivate their employees in terms of carrying out activities and increase work as desired.

METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted at the Education Office of Labuhan Batu Regency which is located at Jalan Menara, No. 7, Rantauprapat, Labuhan Batu Regency, North Sumatra. Meanwhile, the research time was carried out from October 2022 to January 2022.

A hypothesis is a temporary answer to a research problem, until it is proven through the collected data. The hypotheses of the study are:

- H1: Work facilities have a significant effect on motivation
- H2: Communication has a significant effect on motivation
- H3: Work facilities have a significant effect on performance
- H4: Communication has a significant effect on performance
- H5: Motivation has a significant effect on performance
- H6: Work facilities have a significant impact on performance through motivation
- H7: Communication has a significant effect on performance through motivation

Figure: Conceptual Framework

RESULTS

A. t test

Sub Model II t Test Results

Coefficients^a

Type	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	21,330	9,522		2,240	,029
Work Facilities	,240	,147	,205	2,628	,019
Communication	,297	,136	,274	2,192	,032
Motivation	,038	,105	,045	2,361	,020

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source : Primary Data Processed, 2022

On the table, a statistical test t is obtained, as follows:

- 1) Motivation Variable (Z), with a probability level of 0.020. Thus it can be concluded $P = 0.020 < \alpha = 0.05$, then accept the hypothesis that states the motivational variable has a significant effect on performance.
- 2) Work Facility Variable (X1), with a probability level of 0.019. With demikian it can be concluded $P = 0.019 < \alpha = 0.05$, then accept the hypothesis that states the variable of work facilities has a significant effect on performance.
- 3) Communication Variable (X2), with a probability level of 0.032. Thus it can be concluded $P = 0.032 < \alpha = 0.05$, then accept the hypothesis that states communication variables have a significant effect on performance.

Thus can be compiled the path analysis equation as follows : $Y = 0.205 X1 + 0.274 X2 + 0.045 Z$

The analysis equation model means:

- 1) Work Facility Variable (X1) = 0.205. A work facility variable that is positively marked means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that any addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the work facility variable will increase the value of the performance variable by 0.205 per one unit score.
- 2) Communication variable (X2) = 0.274. A communication variable that is positively marked means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that every addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the communication variable will add a performance variable value of 0.274 per one unit score.
- 3) Motivation Variable (Z) = 0.045. A motivation variable marked positive means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit of the var score will increase the value of the performance variable by 0.045 per one unit score.

B. sobel test

Mediation hypothesis testing can also be done with a procedure developed by Sobel and known as the sobel test. The Sobel test is carried out by testing the strength of indirect influence X to Y through Z, as follows:

$$Z = \frac{ab}{\sqrt{(b^2SE_a^2 + a^2SE_b^2)}}$$

Where:

a = regression coefficient of an independent variable to the mediation variable

b = regression coefficient of the mediation variable to the dependent variable

SEa = standard error of estimation of the influence of independent variables on mediation variables

SEb = standard error of estimation of the influence of mediation variables on dependent variables

The following are the results of the sobel test with variables of work facilities on kinerja through motivation.

$$t = \frac{0.166 \times 0.045}{\sqrt{(0.045^2 \times 0.181^2) + (0.166^2 \times 0.105^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.166 \times 0.045}{\sqrt{0.00006634102 + 0.0003038049}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.00747}{0.00037014592}$$

$$t = 20,181$$

From the results of the calculation of the sobel test above, it gets a t value of 20,181, so that a calculated t value of 20,181 > t table 3,887 is obtained, it can be concluded that the motivation variable is able to mediate the relationship of the influence of work facilities on performance.

The following are the results of the sobel test with variables of communication to performance through motivation.

$$t = \frac{0.100 \times 0.045}{\sqrt{(0.045^2 \times 0.168^2) + (0.100^2 \times 0.105^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.100 \times 0.045}{\sqrt{0.0000571536 + 0.00011025}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.0045}{0.0001674036}$$

$$t = 26,881$$

From the results of the calculation of the sobel test above getting a t value of 26,881, so that a calculated t value of 26,881 > t table 3,887 was obtained, it can be concluded that the motivation variable is able to mediate the relationship of the influence of communication on performance.

C. path analysis

Figure: Model II Sub Path Diagram

The results of the analysis showed that the direct influence provided by the Work Facility (X1) on Performance (Y) was 0.205. Meanwhile, the indirect influence of Work Facilities (X1) on Performance (Y) through Motivation (Z), which is $0.166 \times 0.274 = 0.045$. Then the total effect given by the Work Facility variable (X1) on Performance (Y) is a direct influence coupled with an indirect influence, which is $0.205 + 0.045 = 0.25$. Based on the results of the above calculations, it can be known that the value of direct influence is 0.205 and indirect influence by 0.045, which means that the value of direct influence is greater than the value of indirect influence. These results show that indirectly the variable Work Facility (X1) through Motivation (Z) has no significant effect on Performance (Y).

The results of the analysis showed that the direct influence given by Communication (X2) on Performance (Y) was 0.274. Meanwhile, the indirect influence of Communication (X2) on Performance (Y) through Motivation (Z), which is $0.100 \times 0.045 = 0.0045$. Then the total influence that the communication variable (X2) exerts on Performance (Y) is a direct influence coupled with an indirect influence, which is $0.274 + 0.0045 = 0.27$. Based on the results of the above calculations, it can be known that the value of direct influence is 0.274 and an indirect influence of 0.0045, which means that the value of direct influence is greater than that of the value of indirect influence. These results show that indirectly the variable Career Development (X2) through Work Motivation (Z) has no significant effect on Job Satisfaction (Y).

Table 4.17 Total Influence Values

No.	Influence	Direct Influence	Indirect Influence	Total Influence
1	X1 → Y	0.205	$0.166 \times 0.274 = 0.045$	0.25
2	X2 → Y	0.274	$0.100 \times 0.045 = 0.0045$	0.27

DISCUSSION

D. The Effect of Work Facilities on Motivation

The variable of work facilities has a positive and significant effect on motivation at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The work facility variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.166 has a unidirectional effect, which means that any addition or increase

in the value of one unit score of the work facility variable will increase the motivational value of the employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office by 0.166 per one unit score.

Based on the results of the first hypothesis test, it is known that work facilities have a significant influence on the motivation of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This is supported by research conducted by Jufrizen and Fadilla Puspita Hadi (2021), revealing that work facilities have an influence on motivation.

E. The Effect of Communication on Motivation

Communication variables have a positive and significant influence on motivation at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The communication variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.100 has a unidirectional effect, which means that every addition or increase in the value of one unit of communication variable score will increase the motivation value of Labuhanbatu Education Office employees by 0.100 per one unit score.

Based on the results of the second hypothesis test, it is known that communication has a significant influence on the motivation of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This is supported by research conducted by Sundari and Antin Okfitasari (2017), revealing that communication has a significant influence on motivation.

F. The Effect of Work Facilities on Performance

Work facility variables have a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The work facility variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.205 has a unidirectional effect, which means that any addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the work facility variable will increase the performance value of the employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office by 0.205 per one unit score.

Based on the results of the third hypothesis testing, it is known that work facilities have a significant influence on the performance of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The results of this study are supported by research conducted by Adhie Fasha Nurhadian (2019), which states that work facilities have a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

G. The Effect of Communication on Performance

Communication variables have a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The communication variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.274 has a unidirectional effect, which means that any increase in the value of one unit score of the communication variable will increase the performance value of the Labuhanbatu Education Office by 0.274 per unit score.

Based on the results of the fourth hypothesis test, it is known that communication has a significant influence on the performance of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Zackharia Rialmi and Morsen (2020) also states that communication has a positive and significant effect on performance.

H. The Effect of Motivation on Performance

The motivation variable has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The motivation variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.045 has a unidirectional influence which means that every addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the motivation variable will increase the performance value of Labuhanbatu Education Office employees by 0.001 per one unit score.

Based on the results of the fifth hypothesis test, it is known that motivation has a significant influence on the performance of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This is in accordance with research conducted by Siti Mustaqimah, Karnadi and Riska Ayu Pramesthi (2022), which found that motivation can improve employee performance.

I. Work Facility Improvement of Performance through Motivation

Based on the results of the calculation of the Sobel test, it is known that the t value is 20,181, so that the calculated t value of 20,181 > t table 3,887 is obtained, it can be concluded that the motivation variable is able to mediate the relationship of the influence of work facilities on performance. And based on the analysis of the pathway, it is known that the magnitude of the influence of work facilities (X1) on the performance (Y) of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office is 25%, which consists of a direct influence of 20.5% and an indirect influence of work facilities (X1) on performance (Y) through Motivation (Z) of 4.5%. The results of this calculation show that the direct influence of work facilities (X1) on performance (Y) is greater than its indirect

influence. Thus it can be said that work facilities are effective in improving performance, with the word la in it can be affirmed that work facilities (X1) have an influence if there is an increase in employee performance in carrying out duties.

Based on the results of the sixth hypothesis test, it is known that work facilities through motivation have an influence on the performance of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The results showed that motivation has a role in mediating the influence of work facilities on performance.

J. The Effect of Communication on Performance through Motivation

Based on the results of the sobel test calculation, it is known that the t value is 26,881, so that the calculated t value of 26,881 > t table 3,887 is obtained, it can be concluded that the motivation variable is able to mediate the relationship of the influence of communication on performance. And based on the analysis of the path, it is known that the effect of communication (X2) on the performance (Y) of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office is 27%, which consists of a direct influence of 27.4% and an indirect influence of communication (X2) on performance (Y) through Motivation (Z) of 0.6%. The results of this calculation show that the direct influence of communication (X2) on performance (Y) is greater than its indirect influence. Thus, it can be said that communication is effective in improving performance, in other words, it can be emphasized that communication (X1) has an influence if there is an increase in employee performance in carrying out duties.

Based on the results of the seventh hypothesis test, it is known that communication through motivation has an influence on the performance of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The results showed that motivation has a role in mediating the influence of communication on performance.

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of work facilities on the performance of employees of the will be greater if it is carried out through motivation. The direct effect of work facilities on employee performance is smaller than the indirect influence of work facilities on performance. It can be concluded that motivation is able to mediate the influence of work facilities on performance. Work facilities have a positive and significant effect on motivation. This means that this condition proves that the provision of work facilities can increase employee motivation.

REFERENCES

1. A.S. Moenir. 2010. Public Service Management in Indonesia. Jakarta : Bumi Aksara.
2. Anwar, Sanusi. 2011. Business Research Methodology. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
3. Argensia. 2014. Analysis of the Effect of Job Satisfaction and Motivation on Employee Performance with Organizational Commitment as an Intervening Variable in the Office of The Minister and Customs and Excise Service type B Customs Associate Medan. Journal of Economists, Volume 17, Number 2.
4. Agustini, Fauzia. 2011. Advanced Human Resource Management (First Edition). Medan: Madenatera Publishers.
5. Ghozali, Imam. 2018. Multi variate analysis applications with IBM SPSS 25 programs. Jakarta : Diponegoro University Publisher.
6. Hussein Umar.2013. Research Methods for Thesis and Thesis, Rajawali, Jakarta.
7. Handoko, T. Hani (2012). HumanResources Personnel Management. Second Edition. Yogyakarta: BPFE.
8. Hasibuan, S.P Malayu (2009). Organization and Basic Motivation for Productivity Improvement. 7th printing. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara.
9. Hamali, Arif Yusuf (2016). Understanding Human Resource Management: Strategies for Managing Employees. First Printing. Yogyakarta: CAPS.
10. Kadarisman, M. 2013. Human Resource Development Management. Jakarta: PT. King Grafindo Persada.
11. Cashmere. 2016. Human Resource Management. 1st printing. Jakarta : PT. King Grafindo Persada.
12. Mangkunegara, Anwar, Prabu. 2014. Enterprise Human Resource Management. Bandung: PT. Juvenile Rosdakarya.
13. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu (2017). Management of Corporate Human Resources. 12th printing. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya
14. Nisa' Ulul Mafra (2017). The Effect of Competence and Communication on the Performance of PT. Bukit Asam (Persero), Tbk Kertapati Palembang Pier Unit. Journal of Management: Vol. 2, No. 1.

14. Priansa, Donni June (2018). HR Planning and Development. London: Alfabeta.
15. Rina Erla Anasari, Nanik Suryani. (2015). The Effect of Leadership, Work Environment, and Office facilities on the Performance of Village Apparatus in Limpung District, Batang Regency. Journal of Economic Education Analysis 4 (1). Semarang: Universitas Negeri Semarang, Indonesia.
16. Rini Astuti and Oki Prima Anugrah Lesmana (2018). The Effect of Work Motivation and Workload on Nurse Performance at Mitra Medika General Hospital Medan. Journal of Management: Vol. 6, No. 2.
17. Sutrisno, Edy. 2011. Organisasi Culture (1st Edition). Jakarta : Kencana Publisher (Prenada Media Group).
18. Simanjuntak, Payaman J. 2011. Performance Evaluation Management. 3rd Edition, Jakarta: Fakultas UI.
19. Wibowo. 2017. Behavior in Organizations (2nd Edition, 4th Printing). Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada Publishers.

Cite this Article: Mursal Rambe, Cut Fitri Rostina, Sofiyan, Robert Tua Siregar (2023). The Influence of Work and Communication Facilities on Employee Performance at The Education Department of Labuhan Batu with Motivation as an Intervening Variable. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 6(2), 1244-1251